

Supporting information

Measurement cell for *in situ* elemental mapping of (photo-) catalytically active substances in wet soft matter samples by micro X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy

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Figure S 1: Exploded view of the foil-sandwich configuration.

Figure S 2: Picture of drying membrane sample over time from wet (0 min) to dry a) covered with foil and b) uncovered in foil-sandwich cell.

Figure S 3: Elemental distribution of a) Co K_α (6.9 keV) and b) W L_α (8.4 keV) for a covered and uncovered sample in foil-sandwich configuration over time.

Figure S 4: Smoothed and normalized $W L_{\alpha}$ (8.4 keV) intensity histograms of a) covered and b) uncovered sample showing intensity change over time.

Figure S 5: μ XRF sum spectra (selected area: 5.5x5.5 mm) of the foil-sandwich (orange) as well as of a thicker cell base A (blue) and a thinner cell base C (green) of the developed measurement cell with 0.5 μ g of Co deposited. For each cell, two different positions were probed. Energy range 0 to 25 keV, Cl K_{α} (2.6 keV), Ar K_{α} (2.9 keV), Co K_{α} (6.9 keV), Compton peak (18.9 keV) and Rh K_{α} (20.2 keV).

Figure S 6: Picture of three exemplary membrane filters with selected area (green square, 3.3x3.3 mm) a) directly after insertion into the measurement cell and b) after 15 min. c) Corresponding exemplary Cu K α (8.0 keV) element maps of the selected area.

Figure S 7: Sum spectra of selected area (see SI Fig 5c) green square, 3.3 x 3.3 mm) of element maps of 10 filter membranes soaked in Cu standard solution measured using developed measurement cell. The thick line represents first measurement and thin line second measurement. a) Energy range 0 to 25 keV, Ar K_α (2.9 keV), Cu K_α (8.0 keV) Cu K_β (8.9 keV), Compton peak (18.9 keV) and Rh K_α (20.2 keV) and b) enlarged Cu K_α signal in energy range from 7.8 to 8.3 keV.

Membrane Loading Setup

Figure S 8: Pictures of membrane loading cell setup. a) overview image, b) image of assembled cell, c) setup flow chart and d) exploded view of loading cell.

The membrane loading setup comprises three main components: the loading cell, a KNF SIMDOS®10 FEM 1.10 TT.18 RC-P diaphragm liquid dosing pump, and a modified Schlenk flask with two GL14 threads as a reservoir. All components are connected by BOLA 1/8" OD 1/16" ID FEP tubing, via Idex PEEK flangeless 1/4-28

UNF flat bottom fittings to the pump and loading cell, and via BOLA GL14 HT laboratory screw joints to the reservoir.

The loading cell's bottom distributor and top cover are printed with the Formlabs Form 4 MSLA 3D printer using Formlabs Clear Resin V5. The unloaded sample is placed on the distributor and covered by a nylon mesh cutout. The sealing silicone O-ring between the cell parts is compressed by an external aluminum frame with six M3x30 hex bolt and respective washers and nuts. All loading experiments were performed at a flow rate of 10 mL min⁻¹.